

Design for Wellbeing

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Theoretical paper

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Abstract:

This paper reviews a range of theories on the development and promotion of wellbeing, in order to explain how designed objects can support positive ways of living and people's sense of a valued self in a harmonious world. We propose that designed objects and systems can promote wellbeing in a wide variety of ways. It is not necessarily the case that the most pleasant and easy-to-use products are the most supportive of wellbeing. People may find challenge and difficulty, and a balance between positive and negative, more beneficial in the long run.

We suggest that by drawing on theories and research from areas like psychology, sociology, health studies, and anthropology it should be possible to devise wellbeing-promoting design heuristics. Wellbeing can be supported by encouraging and enabling effective action, prediction and control, satisfying social interaction, and mindfulness, physical involvement and enjoyment.

Research on wellbeing suggests that it results from what people themselves actively do and decide, rather than what is supplied for them. Perhaps an important way of designing for wellbeing is to design the (metaphorical) space that enables people to 'do wellbeing' for themselves.

Key words: wellbeing; flow; personal development; universal design; responsible design

Introduction

The wellbeing of users is not the only aim of design, but most designers would be pleased to think that their work contributes to people's wellbeing, and most would aim to avoid doing work that damages wellbeing, in spite of Papanek's (1985) famous accusation that only a very few professions are more harmful than industrial design. It is important that designed objects are not damaging, frustrating, or irritating in themselves, and it is beneficial if they help to remove barriers and difficulties. Providing immediate pleasure and enjoyment is good, too. These have been major concerns of designers and design writers for a long time.

In this paper, using ideas and theories about wellbeing, mainly from psychology and sociology, we will argue that there are other ways in which design can support wellbeing. These ideas can help to develop a set of guidelines or heuristics for design for wellbeing, as well as a shift in emphasis from designing individual objects to seeing designed objects as part of a network of experiences and services to enhance wellbeing.

Research on wellbeing

Although ideas about wellbeing in philosophy and religion are very old, and nineteenth century social science, as in Freud and Durkheim, had ideas about causes and definitions of wellbeing, a systematic concern with what has become called 'positive psychology' is fairly recent, mainly starting from the ideas of Carl Rogers (Rogers, 1980/1995), Abraham Maslow (Maslow, 1971) and Ivan Illich (Illich, 1975). Snyder and Lopez (2005) and Huppert, Baylis and Keverne (2005) give a cross-section of current research in positive psychology. In contrast with earlier writings, research over the last twenty or thirty years has become much more empirical, using a variety of indicators of adjustment, health, contentment, and effective functioning to evaluate theories of wellbeing. This literature suggests a distinction between three positive states: absence of deprivation and suffering, immediate pleasure and enjoyment, and deeper, longer-term engagement and satisfaction, which might arise either from social engagement or from involvement with tasks and activities. It is suggested that these work in different ways. Removing suffering will stop us feeling bad, but doesn't in itself help us to feel good. Immediate pleasures are enjoyable, but we quickly habituate to pleasant things and need escalation and constant variety to maintain enjoyment. Engagement and satisfaction, on the other hand, may result from activities which may not be immediately experienced as positive (and may well not be relaxing), but are valued in retrospect, and are

seen as being capable of making a positive change in the individual, which in turn may lead to long-term benefits (Seligman, 2003). This last process could be called ‘deep satisfaction’, and its potential for enabling personal development makes it an important component of the wellbeing literature.

Overall, this literature suggests to us that as well as improving things for people by removing unpleasantnesses and difficulties, designers might aim to enhance wellbeing in three general ways: enabling effective and involving action, with an awareness of prediction and control; encouraging satisfying social interaction; and promoting mindfulness, physical involvement and enjoyment. Removing discomfort and irritation has to be worthwhile, of course, and this area is well covered in writings on cognitive ergonomics and universal design. It will be mentioned below where it might be combined with the other three goals.

Below we suggest some specific ways in which those general goals might be followed. These might be used as guidelines for designers: the beginnings of a pattern language (Alexander, Ishikawa, and Silverstein, 1977) for design for wellbeing. The references cited in the lists of guidelines at the end of each section give some support for the principles, sometimes empirically based, sometimes not. There are some principles which the authors have derived from their own experience (as psychologist and designer, and as educators): we hope these will seem reasonable and self-evident to the reader. It is necessary to validate these principles against actual design examples, of course. We give some examples in the paper, but finding more examples, and testing out these principles in action research, is an ongoing project.

Action, prediction and control

Csikszentmihalyi’s (1990) concept of ‘flow’ guides much thinking here. Flow is a state in which people become deeply, effortlessly, involved in what they are doing, lose both self-consciousness and track of time, and experience a sense of control and satisfaction. This is usually associated with activities where there are clear goals with immediate feedback, where the task is challenging and requires skill, and the level of skill required matches the level of skill available. Activities which require extendible skill levels, so that challenge can be increased to match increasing skills, are particularly good candidates for providing flow experiences. Designing for flow is mainly a matter of task design, or perhaps of developing devices with the potential for a wide range of creative uses at a wide range of levels of skill

(like the pencil and the piano: the sailboat and the violin also qualify, though the high levels of skill required to get some appropriate use out of them might make initial learning a non-flow experience), but transparency of action and clear, immediate feedback are important components of the flow experience, and can be the results of thoughtful design. Also making things that ‘just work well’ increases the possibility of creative engagement. Lego bricks are a system which enables play and creativity at a wide range of levels, and so is fundamentally ‘flow-friendly’, but this is supported by the fact that the bricks themselves work so well: they fit together easily and firmly, can be used to make strong, stable structures, and are robust and durable. Sharp knives and easily controllable burners are not an integral part of the flow experience some people have from cooking, but they are a useful support for a full level of involvement in the task.

Similarly, products which give clear guidance about how they can be used, and allow a sense of control and predictability, will support satisfying interaction. It might be useful to avoid too much automation: there should be some relationship between the effort put in and the chances of success and the quality of the outcome. Bread making machines allow those with little expertise or spare time to make their own bread, but giving a variety of controls, allowing the use of a variety of ingredients, and supplying a recipe book (especially if it gives guidance for experimentation) gives the machine more wellbeing-promoting possibilities than one in which one just inserted a pre-packed module and pressed the ‘go’ button. The significance of levels of control and flexibility varies with the basic task, of course. Many washing machines have as wide a range of controls and possibilities as bread making machines – but few users take advantage of this to develop their washing skills and produce ever more enjoyable and satisfying loads of washing. In high-tech products increasing the range of things you can change, and the promise of (unnecessary) functions is attractive, but satisfying products would limit this ‘feature creep’ to those that allow useful and constructive alternatives.

Although some games, like chess, fully allow for the flow experience, some computer game design theorists have made a useful case for designing *toys*, not *games*:

“According to Will Wright, his Sim City is not a game at all, but a toy. Wright offers a ball as an illuminating comparison: it offers many interesting behaviours, which you may explore. You can bounce it, twirl it, throw it, dribble it. And, if you wish, you may use it in a game: soccer, or basketball, or whatever. But the

game is not intrinsic in the toy; it is a set of player-defined objectives overlaid on the toy.

Just so Sim City. Like many computer games, it creates a world, which the player may manipulate, but unlike a real game, it provides no objective. Oh, you may choose one: to see if you can build a city without slums, perhaps. But Sim City itself has no victory conditions, no goals; it is a software toy.

A toy is interactive. But a game has goals.” (Kortikyan, 1994: n.p.)

So games are limiting, compared with toys, but for those of us who aren't creative, they may help to get round the helplessness of having toys that we don't have the imagination to play with. To the extent that they're open to user modification, they can become toy-like, and develop more or less structured game versions, like the various versions of floorball described by Pantzar, Shove and Hand (2005). Since the best games (like the best stories and some of the best music) are communally authored over long periods of time, they may have evolved to be satisfying, flow-possible experiences which can enhance wellbeing.

The guidelines are

- Provide challenges which match people's level of skill
 - and flexibly match changing levels of skill (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990)
- Provide a match between effort and chances of success (Seligman, 1975)
- Allow a sense of prediction and control of what's going on (Seligman, 1975, Langer 1983)
- Allow people to express their meaning in action
 - without that stopping other people doing the same (Illich, 1973)
- Allow them to relate desires and goals (Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton, 1981; Csikszentmihalyi, 1991)

Satisfying social interaction

Design for social interaction is partly a matter of designing convivial social spaces: sociopetal rather than sociofugal layouts (Hall, 1966), or spaces that allow flexible shifting between privacy and intimacy and broader social contact. This is one aspect of Alexander's pattern language (Alexander, Ishikawa and Silverstein, 1977) for architectural design, or Jane Jacob's (1992) ideas about neighbourhood structure. It could also be providing easy-to-use,

flexible communication channels which allow users to design their own interaction systems, as has happened with SMS messaging, or with social networking software like MySpace or Orkut on the Internet. Some of these allow for experimentation and development of new forms of social contact, but they may have the anomic drawback of undermining expectations of social behaviour and controls on it, as in allowing electronic bullying.

Design to help people overcome the inevitable deficiencies in how we present ourselves (given that none of us is as tidy, clean, organised, or socially competent as we would like to seem) could benefit from Goffman's ideas on self-presentation and managing spoiled identity (Goffman, 1959, 1963). Universal design provides a way of supporting those with disability without stigmatising them – and a way in which all can benefit from disability-supporting design. Alternatively design can support people in making the effects of disability unobtrusive and easily managed, as with the Novopen insulin injector for diabetics (Novo Nordisk, 2006), or can allow people to project themselves as whole, valid people, as do wheelchairs which look like lifestyle accessories or stylish furniture, rather than looking like medical appliances.

In the second author's research on how people valued craft objects (interviews carried out March - October 2002 with 30 Finnish respondents, 20 female and 10 male), as well as themes of connection to family, history and loved ones, a further social theme emerged: objects were valued as the production of people that the owners respected and admired. A debased version of this is the endorsed or 'designer' product, which is sold (and perhaps valued) on the basis of a tenuous link with some famous person. A striking feature of this research was how ready people were to ascribe personal identity and social links to some of the objects they owned. This happened both through linkage to the designer or maker but also through the memories and meanings connected to the product.

The importance of the past, personal, family, or social, either as a way of providing reassurance and rootedness, or as a way of judging progress and development, is a recurrent theme in accounts of what people value and find uplifting. Perhaps this suggests that retro design can have non-superficial benefits. It also suggests that systems should allow people to preserve durable traces of what has gone before, and make them easily available in the sometimes distant future.

The guidelines are:

- Encourage/enable high levels of social interaction – a useful approach is in removing barriers to social interaction for those who have difficulty in achieving it.
- Allow presentation of oneself as the kind of person one would like to be taken as - and allow other people to go along with that pretence gracefully (Goffman, 1957)
- Allow people to manage stigma, handicap or shortcomings (Goffman, 1963)
We say ‘manage’ rather than ‘conceal’ here, because some wellbeing suggestions are about authenticity, and living successfully with stigma could support wellbeing better than effectively concealing it.
- Allow people to experiment with being the kind of people they might realistically become (there is evidence about the damaging effects of unrealistic ‘fantasy’ compared with more realistic ‘daydreaming’: Baylis, 2005)
- Provide a stable sense of how people should behave with each other (Durkheim, 1893/1984)
- Support people in expressing love, being loved and connected to other people
- Remind them of/link them with people for whom they have admiration and respect
- Allow them to relate past and present (Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton, 1981; Csikszentmihalyi, 1991)

Mindfulness, physical involvement and enjoyment

Designs should be beautiful, enjoyable or fun, because such things are good in themselves, but some research suggests that there can be longer-term well-being effects, too. Barbara Fredrickson’s (2001, 2003) ‘Broaden and Build’ theory suggests that we become more open and flexible after positive experiences, which then leads to our being able to build enduring personal responses to allow us to experience more positive experiences in future, in an ‘upward spiral’. This is supported by the work of Alice Isen and collaborators (Isen, Daubman and Nowicki, 1987), who found that positive experiences improved people’s performance on ‘creative ingenuity’ tasks. The ‘positive experiences’ used in these studies are rather trivial - being given a bag of sweets or watching a few minutes of an amusing movie: seeing the Alessi ‘Te ò’ strainer which amuses Don Norman in his 2004 book “Emotional Design”, enjoying the animated icon bar on an Apple computer, or being

entranced by the grace and simplicity of an Alvar Aalto chair seems likely to give us even more of a positive boost.

Ellen Langer's research (1990), suggests that there are psychological benefits from increasing awareness and focussing on the immediate moment, or 'mindfulness', an idea familiar from many religions and philosophies. Novelty and unpredictability are likely to jog us back into mindfulness, but subtle variations and unexpectednesses may help to remind us to pay attention and be present, even with familiar objects. Holm (1965) shows how shifting symmetries and subtly false reflections add depth and interest to Northwest Coast Native American art. Symmetry and deliberate mistakes also exist in traditional Karelian towels with rich embroidery in symmetrical decorative figures where there is still always one mistake that the woman making the towel puts in the decoration. Such reminders of imperfection and thus also of the unexpected in life are a feature in many traditional decorative arts. The pleasure in the unexpected is, of course, also applied in contemporary design. One typical example is the shoe trend of designing various patterns (such as animal tracks) on shoe soles that may privately please the owner but can also unexpectedly form charming prints on the ground for everyone to see if they happen to walk on sand or snow.

Robert Emmons and Michael McCullough (2003) found that people who reminded themselves daily of their 'blessings', things in their lives that they felt gratitude for, reported higher levels of happiness than others who reflected on hassles or on neutral topics. This focussed mindfulness can be encouraged by objects in someone's life, as with things which reinforce a sense of rootedness or links with valued others, as discussed above.

Wit is a personal and socially positive feature of design. McAlhorne and Stuart (1996), in introducing a survey of smile-inducing graphic design, point out the following benefits of wit in design:

- It wins time [by catching people's attention]
- It invites participation
- It gives the pleasure of decoding
- It gives a reward
- It amuses
- It gets under the guard
- It forms a bond
- It goes deeper
- It is memorable

Several of these overlap with our general principles.

Research that suggests that people who have higher levels of physical activity are happier than others (Biddle and Ekkekakis, 2005). Product design is a major part of the attractiveness and usability of sporting equipment, which can encourage people to take physical exercise. Equipment can be designed to support developing levels of expertise or fitness, and so encourage developmental involvement in an activity. There is always a danger, though, of making a readily accessible activity into a 'designer sport' which can only be practiced effectively with the right equipment and some inconvenience. Oksanen-Särelä and Timonen (2005) hint at this problem in the transformation of walking into 'Nordic walking', and Valkonen (2005) discusses how the rather simple but valuable physical activity of sleeping can be turned into a manufactured and marketed pleasure.

The guidelines are:

- Give people (perhaps unexpected) positive experiences, which indirectly promotes wellbeing by increasing their openness and flexibility (Fredrickson, 2003)
- Encourage/enable people to be more aware of the immediate moment (Langer, 1990)
- Encourage people to be aware of and reflect on positive aspects of their lives (Emmons and McCullough, 2003; Seligman, 2003)
- Encourage high levels of physical activity (Biddle and Ekkekakis, 2005)

Designing wellbeing systems

The guidelines above could be applied to individual processes or services, but perhaps there is a wider way in which design can support wellbeing. For example, the Finnish ISAK

Independent living centre, together with David Industries, has developed Senior Line gym equipment. The gym equipment is made suitable for older people:

“Their ease of use, together with their optimal seat heights and training postures, creates a clear and safe training environment for the elderly. Anatomically correct exercise options and load modelings together with adjustable movement limiters enable the same machines to be used in preventive and therapeutical training as well as in normal training.”

ISAK (2006: n.p.)

- but the bigger design concept is that the customer has the possibility of special guidance for gym training, and the gym organises sessions that give the senior citizens the opportunity to meet people similar to themselves in living circumstances (and so promote social contact) as they keep fit, and so remain able to take care of themselves and to live in their own homes. The design for wellbeing is the overall package, not just the product design of the equipment.

Another commercial example is in interior decoration, which is popular and profitable in many countries. But this does not mean that all the design work is done by interior designers: it means that people themselves want to do it. Designers evolve the fabrics, furniture, paint ranges, and the other components available in the stores, but many hardware store chains also now provide free interior designer consulting in their shops. So it is both designing components that people can use in their own designs (using their own creativity and sense of identity) and also providing services (consulting to aid the customer in doing their own designs) that form the work of a designer.

These examples demonstrate the most important point of this paper. The notion of a designer making something complete in itself and ‘producing wellbeing’ is mistaken. It is more useful to think of concepts that combine both products and services, which together might be more effective in supporting the possibility of wellbeing. As Klaus Krippendorf (2006) says:

Design has to shift gears from shaping the appearance of mechanical products [...] to conceptualising artefacts, material or social, that have a chance of meaning something to their users, that aid larger communities, and that support a society that is in the process of reconstructing itself.

Krippendorf (2006), n.p.

So designers might work with healthcare, education, or social services to develop objects and systems that allow people the possibility of being active, developing themselves, experiencing flow - and getting long term satisfaction. Although design tradition in many cases encourages designers to produce some single complete 'thing', the heuristics of wellbeing point out that the feeling of wellbeing is born from individual possibilities, activities, social connections and feelings of growth, and the designer can only make scaffolds for these purposes, not some complete product producing wellbeing.

Conclusion

The heuristics explained in this paper were practically applied in Finland in spring 2006 as material for an innovation camp for a 'wellness tourism' project. The participants in the ideation were mainly design students but some tourism and business students also took part. The heuristics helped the participants to produce ideas for wellness tourism where various opportunities for different sorts of experiences and activities for the visitors were included: sports, games, physical care possibilities, culture, nature, aesthetics, contemplation, different eating experiences and nutrition possibilities, all including the element of supporting the visitor's own interaction. This justified the use of the guidelines as a check list.

Research on wellbeing suggests that it is developed from within: it results from what people do and decide, rather than what is supplied for them. The product should give the user the possibility of being creative and controlling her life. The role of design for wellbeing might be to design the (metaphorical) space that enables people to 'do wellbeing' for themselves, by providing effective tools, convivial environments, engaging toys and games, flashes of fun or beauty, and structures and systems to allow people to make good use of all these things. This reflects a view of design first stated long ago:

Thirty spokes share the wheel's hub;

It is the centre hole that makes it useful.

Shape clay into a vessel;

It is the space within that makes it useful.

Cut doors and windows for a room;

It is the holes which make it useful.

Therefore benefit comes from what is there;

Usefulness from what is not there

Lao Tsu (1973: n.p.)

References

- Alexander, C., Ishikawa, S., Silverstein, M. (1977) *A Pattern Language : Towns, Buildings, Construction*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Baylis, N. (2005) "Relationship with Reality and the Well-being of Young Adults." in Huppert, F., Baylis, N. and Keverne, B. *The Science of Well-Being*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 241-272.
- Biddle, S. and Ekkekakis, P. (2005) "Physically active lifestyle and well-being" in Huppert, F., Baylis, N. and Keverne, B. *The Science of Well-Being*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 141-170.
- Csikszentihalyi, M. (1990) *Flow: the Psychology of Optimal Experience*. New York: Harper and Row.
- Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1991) "Design & Order in Everyday Life". *Design Issues*, 8, 26-34.
- Csikszentmihalyi, M. and Rochberg-Halton, E. (1981) *The Meaning of things: Domestic Symbols and the Self*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Durkheim, E. (1893/1984) *The Division of Labour in Society*. London: Macmillan
- Emmons, R. and McCullough, M. (2003) Counting blessings versus burdens: An experimental investigation of gratitude and subjective well-being in daily life. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 84: 377-389
- Fredrickson, B. (2001) "The Role of Positive Emotions in Positive Psychology; the Broaden-and-Build Theory of Positive Emotions." *American Psychologist*, 56: 218-226.
- Fredrickson, B. (2003) "The Value of Positive Emotions." *American Scientist*, 91: 330-335.
- Goffman, E. (1959) *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life*. New York: Doubleday Anchor.
- Goffman, E. (1963) *Stigma: Notes on the Management of Spoiled Identity*. Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice-Hall.
- Hall, E. (1966) *The Hidden Dimension* Garden City, N.Y.: Doubleday
- Herzberg, F., Mausner, B. and Snyderman, B. (1959) *The Motivation to Work*. New York: John Wiley.
- Holm, B. (1965) *Northwest Coast Indian Art*. Seattle: University of Washington Press.
- Huppert, F., Baylis, N. and Keverne, B. (eds.) (2005) *The Science of Well-Being*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Illich, I. (1973) *Tools for Conviviality*. London: Calder and Boyars.

- ISAK (2006) *Senior Line Concept*. Available at <http://www.isak.fi/eng/cfmldocs/index.cfm?ID=1147>. Accessed April 8, 2006.
- Isen, A., Daubman, K. and Nowicki, G. (1987) "Positive Affect Facilitates Creative Problem Solving." *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 52: 1122-1131.
- Jacobs, J. (1992) *The Death and Life of Great American Cities*. New York: Vintage Books.
- Kortikyan, G (1994) "I Have No words & I Must Design" Interactive Fantasy, no. 2 Available at <http://www.costik.com/nowords.html>. Accessed 28 March 2006.
- Krippendorf, K. (2006) *The Semantic Turn: a New Foundation for Design* London: Taylor and Francis
- Lao Tsu (1973) *Tao Te Ching, trans Gia-Fu Feng and Jane English*. Aldershot: Wildwood House
- Langer, E. (1983) *The Psychology of Control*. London: Sage.
- Langer, E. (1990) *Mindfulness*. Reading, MA: Addison Wesley
- Novo Nordisk (2006) *Diabetes Care* available at <http://www.novonordisk.com/diabetes/default.asp>; accessed 7 April 2006
- McAlhone, B. and Stuart, D. (1996) *A Smile in the Mind*. London: Phaidon.
- Maslow, A. (1971) *The Further Reaches of Human Nature*. New York: Viking Press.
- Oksanen-Säreälä, K. and Timonen, P. (2005) "Diversification of Practice – the Case of Nordic Walking." In Pantzar, M. and Shove, E. (eds.) *Manufacturing Leisure*. Helsinki: National Consumer Research Centre, 198-213.
- Pantzar, M., Shove, E. and Hand, M. (2005) "Innovations in Fun: the Careers and Carriers of Digital Photography and Floorball." In Pantzar, M. and Shove, E. (eds.) *Manufacturing Leisure*. Helsinki: National Consumer Research Centre, 214-234.
- Papanek, V. (1985) *Design for the Real World*. London: Thames and Hudson.
- Rogers, C. (1980/1995) *A Way of Being*. Boston/New York: Houghton Mifflin.
- Seligman, M. (1975) *Helplessness*. San Francisco: Freeman
- Seligman, M. (2003) *Authentic Happiness*. London: Nicholas Brealey Publishing.
- Snyder, C. and Lopez, S. (eds.) (2005) *Handbook of Positive Psychology*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Valtonen, A. (2005) "Sleep: Leisure Pleasure Manufactured in the Market" in Pantzar, M. and Shove, E. (eds.) *Manufacturing Leisure*. Helsinki: National Consumer Research Centre, 103-116.